

Protocol for a Scoping Review: RNA-Based Therapeutic Strategies for Dystrophic Epidermolysis Bullosa (DEB)

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1. Title

RNA-Based Therapeutic Strategies for Dystrophic Epidermolysis Bullosa: A Scoping Review Protocol

2. Type of Review

This is a scoping review aimed at systematically mapping and synthesizing both preclinical and early clinical evidence on RNA-based therapeutic strategies for Dystrophic Epidermolysis Bullosa (DEB). The review seeks to characterize the different RNA modalities, molecular targets, delivery systems, outcomes, and research gaps. This protocol was developed in accordance with the **PRISMA-ScR** guidelines [Tricco AC, Tetzlaff J, Moher D. 2011. *The art and science of knowledge synthesis*. <https://doi.org/frdpd2>].

2.1 Review Stages

The review will be conducted in the following stages:

1. **Search:** A comprehensive search strategy will be developed and executed across multiple databases to identify relevant literature.
2. **Screening:** Identified studies will undergo a two-stage screening process: initial title and abstract screening followed by full-text review to assess eligibility.
3. **Backward Reference Searching:** For all studies that meet the inclusion criteria after full-text review, the reference lists will be examined manually to identify additional relevant studies. This backward searching will continue iteratively until no new eligible studies are found (saturation).
4. **Extraction:** Data will be extracted from included studies using a structured charting form. A pilot extraction will be conducted on a subset to refine the form.
5. **Synthesis:** Extracted data will be synthesized both quantitatively and qualitatively to map key characteristics of the evidence and identify research gaps.
6. **Reporting:** Findings will be reported in a manuscript prepared according to PRISMA-ScR guidelines.

2.2 Current Review Stage

The review has completed the search and screening stages. The current stage is **data extraction and tabulation**. This is the first official preregistration submitted for this project.

2.3 Timeline

- **Start date:** July 20, 2025
- **Planned end date:** September 29, 2025

3. Background

Dystrophic Epidermolysis Bullosa (DEB) is a rare genetic skin disorder caused by mutations in the **COL7A1** gene, resulting in absent or defective type VII collagen (C7), essential for skin integrity. Current therapies are largely palliative. RNA-based therapies offer promising strategies to restore C7 function, but the research landscape is scattered and heterogeneous. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of RNA-based strategies, identify research trends and gaps, and inform future preclinical and clinical studies.

4. Objectives

- **Primary Objective:** Map and characterize RNA-based therapeutic strategies for DEB.
- **Research Questions:**
 1. What RNA-based therapies have been investigated for DEB?
 2. What are the extent, nature, and characteristics of evidence on their safety and efficacy?
 3. What barriers and challenges exist for preclinical and clinical translation?

There are no separate secondary research questions.

5. Expectations

Although scoping reviews do not test formal hypotheses, we anticipate:

- Most evidence will come from preclinical studies.
- Antisense oligonucleotide-mediated exon skipping will be the most frequently investigated approach.
- Outcomes, experimental models, and delivery methods will be heterogeneous.
- Knowledge gaps will be identified regarding long-term safety, durability, and clinical translation.

6. Variables

- **Dependent / Outcome Variables:**

- Efficacy
- Safety
- Type VII collagen (C7) expression
- **Independent / Intervention Variables:**
 - Antisense oligonucleotides (AONs)
 - siRNA
 - miRNA
 - RNA trans-splicing
 - Therapeutic mRNA
 - RNA-guided CRISPR (e.g., Cas13)
 - RNA aptamers
- **Additional Variables / Covariates:**
 - Citation (author, year, country)
 - Experimental model (cell lines, animal models, clinical trials)
 - Delivery method (viral, non-viral, topical, systemic)
 - Developmental stage (preclinical or clinical)
 - Target mutation/exon
 - Reported limitations

7. Software

- **Rayyan:** Screening and deduplication
- **Zotero:** Reference management
- **Microsoft Word:** Manuscript drafting
- **Microsoft Excel:** Data extraction and tabulation
- **SPSS:** Statistical analysis (if applicable)
- **Rawgraphs.io:** Alluvial diagrams, dendrograms, Sankey diagrams

8. Funding

This review is unfunded.

9. Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

10. Overlapping Authorship

No reviewers are co-authors of studies likely to be included; therefore, no overlapping authorships are anticipated.

11. Search Strategy

Databases

- PubMed/MEDLINE, PubMed Central, ClinicalTrials.gov, EU Clinical Trials Register, Europe PMC, DOAJ, SciELO, LILACS, MedRxiv, BioRxiv, CORE, OpenGrey, OATD, Google Scholar

Interfaces

- PubMed/MEDLINE: PubMed (NCBI)
- PubMed Central: PMC
- ClinicalTrials.gov: ClinicalTrials.gov
- EU Clinical Trials Register: EU Clinical Trials Register
- Europe PMC: Europe PMC
- DOAJ: DOAJ
- SciELO: SciELO
- LILACS: LILACS
- MedRxiv, BioRxiv: respective platforms
- CORE: CORE
- OpenGrey: OpenGrey
- OATD: OATD
- Google Scholar: Google Scholar

Grey Literature

- Preprint servers (MedRxiv, BioRxiv)
- Dissertations and theses (OATD)
- Grey literature databases (OpenGrey)

- Manual backward reference searches

12. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

12.1 Inclusion

- Original preclinical (in vitro, in vivo) or clinical (Phase I–III) studies on RNA-based therapies for DEB
- Interventions: AONs, siRNA, miRNA, RNA trans-splicing, therapeutic mRNA, RNA-guided CRISPR (e.g., Cas13), RNA aptamers
- Published between January 2005 and July 2025
- Languages: English, Spanish, Portuguese

12.2 Exclusion

- Studies unrelated to DEB pathophysiology
- Gene-editing without RNA mechanisms (e.g., CRISPR-Cas9 alone)
- Reviews, commentaries, or studies without original data
- Non-retrievable full texts

12.3 Framework

PICO:

- Population: Patients with DEB
- Intervention: RNA-based therapies
- Comparison: Not applicable (descriptive scoping review)
- Outcome: Efficacy, safety, C7 expression

12.4 Query Strings / Search Strategy

A comprehensive search strategy was developed and executed across multiple databases to identify literature on RNA-based therapies for dystrophic epidermolysis bullosa (DEB).

Databases searched: PubMed/MEDLINE, PMC, Europe PMC, Google Scholar, DOAJ, LILACS, SciELO, BioRxiv, MedRxiv, BASE, CORE, OATD, and the EU Clinical Trials Register.

Search approach:

- Keywords included disease terms (e.g., “Dystrophic Epidermolysis Bullosa”, “DEB”), therapy terms (e.g., “RNA therapy”, “antisense oligonucleotides”, “RNA trans-splicing”),

“therapeutic mRNA”), and experimental/clinical descriptors (e.g., “preclinical”, “in vitro”, “animal model”, “clinical trial”).

- Advanced terms covering emerging technologies (e.g., siRNA, mRNA, CRISPR-Cas13, aptamers, ADAR) were also included.
- Multilingual coverage: English, Spanish, Portuguese.
- Exclusion criteria: reviews, editorials, conference abstracts/posters, and diagnostic or genomic studies without a therapeutic focus.

Clinical trial registries: Specific searches were performed on ClinicalTrials.gov for DEB interventions involving RNA-based therapies (e.g., antisense oligonucleotides, RNA trans-splicing, therapeutic mRNA, AON).

Documentation: All search strings and raw results for each database are available in the supplementary files deposited in Zenodo. PubMed-based strategies were adapted for other databases to ensure consistency.

12.5 Search Validation

- No formal validation procedure applied.
- Strategy validated by:
 - Broad coverage of databases and grey literature.
 - Iterative refinement of queries.
 - Manual backward reference search to ensure comprehensiveness.

13. Screening

Screening and Selection Decisions

Note: This section documents decisions made during the initial screening and full-text review stages that were not explicitly recorded in the original protocol. This amendment aims to increase transparency and reproducibility; it does not alter the scope or objectives of the scoping review. During the clarification phase of the full-text review, one additional eligible study was identified, resulting in an updated list of included studies (Figure 1).

Initial Screening and Deduplication:

- A total of 1,756 records were identified through database and registry searches.
- Title and abstract review was conducted for all records. Manual deduplication and selection resulted in **67 unique records** for full-text review.
- **Reasons for exclusion at the title/abstract stage:**

- Duplicates: 944
- Wrong population: 300
- Wrong treatment: 40
- Wrong publication type: 402
- Wrong language: 3
- Conflicts requiring third reviewer resolution: 38 (30 excluded, 8 included)

Full-Text Review:

- **67 articles** were reviewed in full.
- **Summary of exclusions and inclusions:**
 - Wrong population: 16
 - Wrong treatment: 8
 - Wrong publication: 20
 - **Total excluded:** 44
 - **Total included:** 23
- **Conflicts resolved by third reviewer: 5**
 - Excluded due to conflict: 4 (wrong publication = 1, wrong population = 2, wrong treatment = 1)
 - Included due to conflict: 1

Final Inclusion:

- **23 studies** included in the analysis.

This documentation clarifies the full-text review process, including how conflicts were resolved, and provides a transparent record of study selection decisions.

Masking: applied for title/abstract screening (reviewers blinded to author/journal).

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection Process.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection: Shows the identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion of studies for the scoping review, including numbers of records retrieved, duplicates removed, exclusions at each stage, conflict resolution, and final included studies.

14. Data Extraction

Entities extracted:

- Metadata: authors, year, journal, country, study design, experimental model.
- Intervention: RNA therapy type, target gene/pathway, delivery method.
- Results: outcomes, main findings, reported limitations.

Data Extraction Process

Note: The following clarifies the data extraction procedure, as it was not explicitly documented in the original protocol. All procedures described were conducted as part of the review and do not alter the scope or objectives of the study.

Process:

1. A pilot extraction was conducted on 2–3 studies to refine the data charting form.
2. Data from all 23 included studies were extracted independently by one reviewer and then reviewed by a second reviewer.
3. Any discrepancies or uncertainties were resolved through discussion and consensus between the reviewers.

Additional Details:

- Independent review ensured accuracy of extracted data.
- Masking or formal reliability testing was not applied; the focus was on careful verification and consensus.

15. Data Management

Data and Supplementary Files Deposited in Zenodo

All data and supplementary materials generated during this scoping review will be deposited in Zenodo to ensure transparency and reproducibility. The following files will be included:

1. Search Records – XLSX, containing all 1,756 results from database and registry searches.
2. Screening Decisions – XLSX, documenting inclusion/exclusion decisions at each stage with reasons for exclusion.
3. Backward Reference Search Records – XLSX, documenting all additional studies identified through manual reference checking.
4. PRISMA Flow Diagram – JPG, illustrating the full screening and selection process.
5. Extracted Data Tables – XLSX, containing all extracted information from the 23 included studies.
6. Descriptive Results Dataset – CSV, prepared for statistical and descriptive analyses.

Note: This deposition clarifies and documents all stages of the review process, including screening decisions, exclusion reasons, and backward reference searches, to provide a complete, transparent, and reproducible record of the review workflow.

15.1 Data Validation

Note: The following describes the data validation process as actually conducted, clarifying procedures not explicitly documented in the original protocol.

1. **Independent Review and Verification:** Data from all included studies were initially extracted by one reviewer and then reviewed by a second reviewer. Any discrepancies or uncertainties were resolved through discussion and consensus.
2. **Cross-Checking Against Source Material:** Key information was verified against the full text of the original articles to ensure accuracy and consistency.
3. **Outliers:** Identification of statistical outliers is not applicable given the descriptive nature of the scoping review. All relevant data are reported.
4. **Retraction Checks:** No systematic post-search retraction screening was conducted; the review relies on the integrity of the databases at the time of search.
5. **Validity Criteria:** Data were considered valid if accurately reflected the source material and confirmed through the reviewer consensus process. Any unresolved discrepancies would have been excluded from synthesis.

Clarification Note: This description reflects the actual procedures carried out, ensuring transparency. While formal inter-rater reliability metrics were not applied, independent review followed by consensus provided a practical approach to verifying accuracy and completeness of extracted data.

16. Quality Assessment

Consistent with scoping review methodology, a formal risk of bias assessment (e.g., Cochrane RoB, GRADE) will not be performed. Instead, quality will be addressed descriptively by reporting study design and limitations as presented by the authors. This provides contextual insight into the strength of the evidence without imposing inappropriate quantitative judgments.

17. Synthesis Plan

The synthesis will follow a narrative, descriptive approach:

1. **Descriptive Mapping:** Summarize the literature landscape using charts and tables (e.g., publication trends, geographical distribution, intervention modalities, delivery methods, and experimental models).

2. **Thematic Analysis:** Identify recurring themes, therapeutic targets, limitations, and author-reported future directions.
3. **Gap Identification:** Highlight gaps in evidence, inconsistencies, or areas requiring more advanced study designs.
4. **Narrative Reporting:** Integrate descriptive and thematic findings into a coherent narrative addressing the guiding research question.

Contingency Plan: If data for specific entities are consistently missing, these will be explicitly reported as literature gaps rather than methodological limitations.

18. Criteria for Conclusions

Conclusions will not rely on inferential statistics or effect size thresholds. Instead, they will be drawn based on:

- Descriptive synthesis of study characteristics.
- Thematic patterns emerging across studies.
- Identification of research gaps.

19. Blinding of Synthesists

Blinding will not be implemented. All reviewers will be aware of the research questions and objectives, as this awareness is essential for a holistic, interpretive synthesis.

20. Synthesis Reliability

Note: This section clarifies the synthesis process, which was not fully documented in the original protocol.

Descriptive and thematic analyses were initially conducted independently by the two reviewers, but this procedure was not formally recorded. Subsequently, the reviewers reconciled differences through discussion, with the lead author overseeing and arbitrating any unresolved issues.

Clarification Note: This amendment documents the actual process followed, ensuring transparency. While independent preliminary syntheses were conducted, the lack of prior documentation prompted this clarification. The approach maintains reliability and reproducibility without altering the study's scope or objectives.

21. Reconciliation of Divergent Decisions

Disagreements between reviewers will first be addressed through discussion. If unresolved, the lead author will review the evidence and make the final determination.

22. Publication Bias

Formal analyses of publication bias (e.g., funnel plots) will not be conducted, as these methods are inappropriate for scoping reviews that do not involve quantitative pooling.

23.Sensitivity and Robustness Checks

Sensitivity analyses will not be conducted, as the review does not involve effect size estimation. Instead, transparency in reporting and documentation of missing data will serve as safeguards against bias.

24.Justification of Synthesis Procedures

- **Data Transformations:** Recoding and categorization of variables (e.g., grouping delivery methods) are necessary to synthesize heterogeneous evidence in a systematic manner.
- **Missing Data:** Non-reported data will be explicitly labeled as “Not Reported” rather than imputed.
- **Narrative Synthesis:** Chosen to map breadth and scope rather than quantify outcomes.
- **Conclusions:** Will emphasize thematic and descriptive insights instead of statistical inference.
- **Reliability:** Use of multiple reviewers with reconciliation ensures accuracy while avoiding impractical blinding.

25.Data Management and Sharing

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, all relevant files will be shared openly:

- **Extraction Matrix:** Complete data extraction sheet (.xlsx).
- **Synthesis Data Files:** Processed datasets in .csv format.
- **Outputs:** Tables, figures, and descriptive analyses in .pdf/.docx.

All files will be deposited in the OSF project associated with this preregistration and made publicly accessible upon completion of the review.

26.Miscellaneous Details

All essential methodological details are captured above. No additional synthesis procedures are planned.